

Type of Tourism Attraction and Revisit Intention of Female Traveller

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ABSTRACT: This research was conducted with the aim of gathering information on the motivations of female tourists to make repeat visits to Yogyakarta. Women were chosen as respondents because women are considered to have maturity and make better decisions in their families, as well in tourism activities. The research was conducted using a non-probability sampling model on 100 respondents who had finished their trip. The survey was carried out at tourist entry points such as at tourist attraction locations, railway stations and airports. There are three variables tested, namely Perceived Satisfaction of Cultural Attraction (CUL), Perceived Satisfaction of Natural Attraction (NAT), and Perceived Satisfaction of Shopping and Culinary Attraction (ShoC). Using the classic assumption test and multiple linear regression, the results show that female travellers have the intention of making a return visit (RI) because of the satisfaction factor on cultural tourist attraction (CUL) and the satisfaction factor on shopping and culinary attraction (ShoC). The attractiveness of Natural Attraction (NAT) does not significantly influence female travellers having intention to revisit.

KEYWORDS: Attraction, Destination, Female Traveller, Intention, Tourism.

INTRODUCTION

Since long time ago, in various studies on consumer behavior, the female segment has often received special attention [1-3]. A number of shifts in the role of women as well as their socio-economic abilities have made women an interesting segment cluster to study [4-6]. Many production companies also recognize that women's behavior, especially in purchasing and household decisions, is of particular interest, women are able to influence purchasing decisions between 70% - 80% [7]. Today's women are able to carry out many roles so that they can take over what men normally do [8, 9]. Likewise with regard to travel activities, women also play a major role in assessing or deciding the purpose of travel in a family [10]. Based on these opinions, it is likely that what is perceived and recommended by women is more widely shared by their families or colleagues.

Women are considered to be more objective in assessing a destination even when planning to make a repeat visit due to being impressed with the destination they have visited [10]. There are many reasons that allow repeat visits in tourism activities for example because of the existence of facilities and amenities, good quality of service, variety of attractions, and overall satisfaction [11, 12]

Yogyakarta is one of the famous destinations in Indonesia. According to data released by the local Tourism Authority mentioned that every year about 5 million tourists come to Yogyakarta. From this data, 90% are domestic tourists, the rest are foreign tourists. Based on the composition, 54% are women and 46% are men. Most of the tourists, which is about 70% of the total, are repeaters, namely those who have been there more than once [13]. Based on this reason, it is important to examine the intention to make repeat visits.

Knowing the perception of revisit intentions, especially from a woman's point of view, is considered important because women are considered to have a central role in a family, their environment, as well as for themselves [7, 8]. What is perceived by the women is expected to be a recommendation for the people around them so that they are more motivated to come to the destination. Apart from that, it will also be known which types of tourism categories are in demand in Yogyakarta. Of course, the perception of the intention to return visits only appears if there is satisfaction obtained from the activities or attractions that have been visited [11, 14, 15]. Therefore, the variable observed in this study is the perception of satisfaction with tourist attractions whether it is nature, culture, or shopping and culinary.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Women role In Travel Decision

The importance of the role of women has been studied in depth by Nahar and Mengo [10] which states that the role of women in decision-making is increasing, such as in matters of economic and financial decisions, freedom of movement, self-esteem, even in sex and reproduction [8]. One of the factors is the various forms of support, both policies and the role of volunteers who defend

women's rights. In tourism, women dominate the decision making of a family's travel plans [9, 16]. A study which conducted in Bangladesh [17] states that women have self-esteem and freedom of mobility with increasing education and their ability to generate revenue economically. In Indonesia, currently there has been a population shift with the increase in the number of working women by 30% higher than in previous years[18]

Revisit Intention

Revisit intention can be explained as something that shows a person's tendency to return to the same place or destination [11, 19-21]. In the tourism business, the intention to make repeat visits is very important because it will foster loyalty which has an impact on reducing marketing costs, increasing potential spending, and even opportunities to increase the number of visits through invitations and referrals to family and colleagues [14]. Factors such as satisfaction, diversity of attractions, service quality, image are considered as triggers for tourists to have repeat visit intentions [12, 14, 21, 22]. In relation to gender roles, research conducted by Yang, et al. [16] found that female visitors tend to have higher repeat visit intentions than male visitors.

Type of Tourism Attraction in Indonesia

Tourism has three main groups of attractions, namely nature-based, cultural-based and artificial-based, but in a more specific segment which is often referred to as special interest tourism there are several market niches such as shopping, culinary, and meeting services or popularly called MICE [23]. Culture-based attractions as an example are cultural diversity, handicraft products such as batik or other arts, art and performance, heritage and museums, historical/ancient monuments, and palaces [24]. Nature-based attractions, for example, are mountains, seas, caves, forests, and ecotourism. In the shopping and culinary attractions group, there can be traditional culinary activities, culinary with a specific atmosphere, while shopping is traditional shopping, traditional markets, shopping for local arts and crafts.

Hypotheses

Referring to the various arguments above, the hypotheses put forward in the study are as follows:

- H1 : Perceived satisfaction on natural tourist attractions influences the intention to revisit
- H2 : Perceived satisfaction on cultural tourism influences the intention to revisit
- H3 : Perceived satisfaction on shopping and culinary tourism influences the intention to return

METHOD

In accordance with the purpose of the research to be conducted, namely, to determine the factors that influence female travelers to have the intention to return to Yogyakarta, the research approach used is a quantitative research model. The analysis used is the classical assumption test and regression. This test is considered relevant because there are not many variables, and the ultimate goal of the study is to determine the influencing factors with only two test variables. The classic assumption test is carried out to ensure that the data and research models that are made are feasible for further testing, namely regression as hypothesis testing. The following is a proposed research model and operational variables.

Figure 1. Research Proposed Model

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Validity and Reliability Test

Based on the results of validity and reliability testing on a sample of 100 respondents with a significance of 5%, if the value of R count greater than R table on credibility less than 0.05 then the statement can be said to be valid and feasible to use as a research instrument [25]. All the instruments are valid than research can be continued. For details see table 1.

Table 1. Validity Test Result for Research Variable Items

Variables	R Count	R table	Comments
NAT1	0,857	0,197	Valid
NAT2	0,854	0,197	Valid
NAT3	0,825	0,197	Valid
CUL1	0,797	0,197	Valid
CUL2	0,798	0,197	Valid
CUL3	0,853	0,197	Valid
SHOC1	0,886	0,197	Valid
SHOC1	0,795	0,197	Valid
SHOC1	0,872	0,197	Valid
RI1	0,848	0,197	Valid
RI2	0,749	0,197	Valid
RI3	0,783	0,197	Valid

The thing to do after showing that all statement variables are suitable as research instruments is to carry out a reliability test with the provision that if the Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.7 then the data is reliable and can be used as a research instrument. Here is the results of the reliability test shows detail at Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability Test Result for Research variable Items

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Comments
NAT	0,799	Reliable
CUL	0,750	Reliable
ShoC	0,810	Reliable
RI	0,704	Reliable

After testing the feasibility of the data in terms of validity and reliability, the next step is to test the assumptions, namely the classical assumption test. This test is carried out in order to ensure that the resulting regression model is the best model in terms of estimation accuracy, does not experience bias, and is consistent [26]. The classic assumption test includes the normality test, heteroscedasticity test, and multicollinearity test.

Normality test

This test was conducted to show whether the data were normally distributed or not and was carried out using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test. The test results show that the asymp.sig value is 0.175 or greater than 0.05 so it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. For detail, please see Table 3.

Table 3. Normality Test Result

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	.87893413
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.076
	Positive	.076
	Negative	-.053
Test Statistic		.076
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.175 ^c

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Multicollinearity test

The multicollinearity test aims to determine whether there is a correlation between the independent variables in the regression model. A good regression model should not have a correlation between independent variables. To find out whether or not multicollinearity exists, it can be seen from the value of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance value (α). The test results show that all variables have a tolerance value greater than 0,10 (where NAT=0,686; CUL=0.584; ShoC=0.500) or the value of VIF less than 10 (NAT=1,457; CUL=1.711; ShoC=2.000) the data shows that there is no multicollinearity. For details, please see at Table 4.

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Result

Variables	Tolerance	VIF	Comments
NAT	0,686	1,457	No Multicollinearity
CUL	0,584	1,711	No Multicollinearity
ShoC	0,500	2,000	No Multicollinearity

Heteroscedasticity test

An important assumption of the classical linear regression model is that the disturbances that appear in the regression are homoscedasticity, that is, all the disturbances have the same variance. The results of the Heteroscedasticity test showed that NAT had a P (Probability) value of 0.734, CUL had a P of 0.450, and ShoC had a P value of 0.983 all probability values greater than 5%, thus the variables proposed in the study did not occur heteroscedasticity.

Table 5. Heteroscedasticities Test Result

Variables	Sig.	Tolerance	Comments
NAT	0,734	>0,05	No heteroscedastic
CUL	0,450	>0,05	No heteroscedastic
ShoC	0,983	>0,05	No heteroscedastic

Hypotheses Testing with Multiple Regression

To test the effect of Perceived Satisfaction of Natural Attraction (NAT), Perceived Satisfaction of Cultural Attraction (CUL), and Perceived Satisfaction of Shopping & Culinary Attraction (ShoC) on Revisit Intention (RI) here used multiple linear regression analysis. In the multiple linear regression analysis model will be tested simultaneously (F test) or partially (t test). The provisions for the significance test for the F test and t test are to accept H_a : if P (probability) ≤ 0.05 means NAT, CUL. and ShoC simultaneously or partially have a significant influence on RI. The results of this test can be summarized in the following table:

Table 6. Linear Regression Result Test

Hypotheses	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Count	Sig t	Comments
(Constant)	2,251					
NAT → RI	0,095	0,058	0,109	1,628	0,107	Rejected
CUL → RI	0,302	0,065	0,339	4,651	0,000	Accepted
ShoC → RI	0,443	0,068	0,511	6,494	0,000	Accepted
F Count	75,531					
Sig F	0,000					
Adjusted R Square	0,693					

Based the data on Table 6, the regression coefficient of X1 (NAT) of 0.095 from all the factors studied means that the NAT variable has a negative relationship with RI. The regression coefficient X2 (CUL) of 0.302 means that the CUL variable has a positive relationship with RI. The regression coefficient X3 (ShoC) of 0.443 means that the ShoC variable has a positive relationship with RI. This informs that increasing Perceived Satisfaction of Shopping & Culinary Attraction will increase Revisit Intention.

Based on the Simultaneous Regression (F Test) the F-count value is 75.531 with probability (p) is 0.000. Based on the provisions of the F test where the probability value (p) is 0.000 greater than or equal to 0.05, it states that NAT, CUL, and ShoC simultaneously affect Revisit Intention.

Based on the Coefficient of Determination (R²) value, the simultaneous influence of NAT, CUL, and ShoC on RI is shown by the Adjusted R Square value of 0.693. This means that 69.3% RI is influenced by NAT, CUL, and ShoC while the remaining 30.7% (100% -69.3%) is influenced by other variables.

Based on the Partial Regression Test (t test) it was found that the effect of NAT on RI obtained a t-count value of 1.628 with probability (p) = 0.107, the results of the t test showed that the probability value (p) > 0.05 so it can be concluded that NAT is NOT significant to RI. The effect of CUL on RI based on the partial regression test, obtained a t-count value of 4.651 with a probability (p) = 0.000. Meanwhile, the results of the t test showed that the probability value (p) <0.05 so it can be concluded that CUL has a significant effect on RI. Based on the partial regression test on the ShoC variable, a t-count value of 6.494 was obtained with a probability (p) = 0.000, while the t-test results obtained a probability value (p) <0.05 so it can be concluded that ShoC has a significant effect on RI.

Discussion

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it shows that female travelers do not like natural tourist attractions. Nature tourism activities are activities that involve a lot of physical effort which is not liked by most women. Some types of natural tourist attractions even require very intensive physical activity with equipment, for example for ecotourism activities. Therefore, it is very natural that women do not like nature tourism. However, it can be seen that female tourists tend to like cultural, culinary and shopping activities. This activity is an important activity for women to express themselves and fulfill their needs. Cultural activities include seeing a number of cultural attractions such as temples, palaces, or viewing performing arts, while culinary and shopping are inseparable joint activities. Women often bring their entire family shopping and enjoying culinary delights.

The implications resulting from this research are how business actors can take advantage of this opportunity to attract the female traveler segment. Increasing a number of shopping tourist attractions, culinary and cultural centers with special services for women is an important priority. This form of special service includes, for example, providing special price discounts for women, special Mother’s Day giving special souvenirs to women, or even special assistants when they are shopping. Through female travelers whose position is as an influencer for families, it is hoped that they will get a larger market segment, especially for the family segment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of tests carried out in stages with the classical assumption test and multiple linear regression testing, it can be concluded that of the three hypotheses proposed H2 and H3 show positive results. The Satisfaction of Cultural Attraction (CUL) and Satisfaction of Shopping and Culinary Attraction (ShoC) has a significant effect on Revisit Intention (RI). However, the Perceived Satisfaction of Natural Attraction (NAT) has no significant effect on Revisit Intention (RI). Thus, the final statement of the three hypotheses proposed is that female tourists who come to Yogyakarta have the intention to return to visit by considering two things,

namely cultural, shopping and culinary attractions. Improving services in the cultural, shopping and culinary attraction aspects by tourism businesses is very likely to increase their market share specifically for the family segment, because the position of women is the influencer in their family.

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